

THE ROLE OF THE FIRST LANGUAGE IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION PROCESS

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Annotation. This article discusses the role of the first language in the second language acquisition process. It compares and contrasts both language acquisition processes. It is obvious that the role of the first language is significant in learning any foreign languages. Each has similar and different stages to discuss.

Key words. Second language acquisition, first language, learner characteristics, linguistic factors, instructional variables, context, purpose, age and acquisition.

The second language learning is a complex process that requires total involvement, total physical, emotional and intellectual response. It is not an easy set of steps that can be programmed in a quick do-it-yourself kit. Anyone who has fluency in a foreign language has achieved this level with the assistance of teacher in the classroom atmosphere.

As every complex process has its own issues, there are some questions in the research of language learning process. We will discuss some of those questions, sorted here into some commonly used topical categories.

The initial one is learner characteristics. In this issue the ethnic, linguistic, cultural and even religious background of learners are involved. Besides that, students' native languages, levels of education, socioeconomic characteristics are also important. These and other issues focus on some variables affecting not only learner's success in learning a foreign language, but also teacher's capacities to enable learner to succeed.

No single question can probe the whole nature of one issue. Linguistic factors take a considerable point in the second language acquisition process. They include the structure of the target language, communication skills, the usage of the language, the difference and commonalities between the first and second language. These profound issues are

central to the discipline of the linguistics. Admittedly, language teacher should be able to speak and receive a language, however, it is not the only skill required. ESL teachers should attain the knowledge to explain the system of the language accurately, such as its phonemes, morphemes, words, sentences and discourse markers.

The usage of authentic materials in ESL classrooms is not new. However, both beginner and specialized teachers have difficulty using and adopting those materials in their teaching sections. These materials include written or spoken materials in the target language used in the classroom unedited. Because of unedited usage, it is often difficult to comprehend them especially for the students lower than intermediate level. Furthermore, choosing and adopting right and suitable materials may cause some challenges for ESL teachers. What main factors should we consider to choose the right material? Topic is the first factor to consider that influence the procedure more than any others do. Skills, language area, time, level of the students are also important in this procedure. However, the most significant, but mostly excluded element is students' needs and interests. There is no point in showing your students political debates or president's speech if they are more interested in the latest news about their famous celebrity.

Some foreign language acquisition successfully takes place outside of the classroom or let's call out of the educational context. Do we get the same achievement in both "natural" environment learning and classroom learning? This one is another issue to be discussed. This includes methodological approaches, textbooks, materials, teaching styles, instructional factors. Teacher should manage the amount of time spent on every single activity. The student should have the balance of the time spent inside and outside the classroom for language learning purposes.

One of the most encompassing issue is the purpose of learning a foreign language. Some students are motivated by the achievement of successful carrier, while others wish to identify the culture of the people of the target language.

By analyzing all those issues above, we cannot find out a magic formula that fits every foreign language learner in every context. Some methods or activities may work well in one classroom, whereas teacher may not able to get acceptable result by using the same method in another classroom atmosphere. Therefore, it is the very point to mention the famous remark of Roger Brown (1966, p.326) which is still true in our methodology: "Psychologists find it exciting when a complex mental phenomenon- something intelligent and slippery – seems about to be captured by a mechanical model. We yearn to see the model succeed. But when, at the last minute, the phenomenon proves too much for the model and darts off on some uncapturable tangent, there is something in us that rejoices the defeat". This field of study is not simple. It is changeable for every learner in every context and in every single time. It is like a puzzle solving activity, that some pieces have already been located, while others are not yet discovered. Teachers' role is to find all those unknown pieces and set them together to make an impressing piece of art.

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